

Silicon ion implantation on austenitic and ferritic stainlesssteels against localized aqueous corrosion

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Abstract

Silicon ion implantation has been used as a surface modification technique in order to improve the corrosion resistance of two stainless steels with similar passive layers but different microstructures, such as AISI 304 (austenitic) and AISI 430 (ferritic). For each steel, different doses of silicon ion implantation (1×10^{14} , 5×10^{14} , 1×10^{15} ions/cm²) at an energy of 80 keV have been tested. Theoretical simulations using the TRIM 96 computer code have been performed in order to estimate the Si implantation profiles. The corrosion resistance of the Si-implanted stainless steels was analysed using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in a 0.5 M NaCl solution. The surface was characterised by Auger electron spectroscopy (AES). The effect of optimum doses of Si-implanted stainless steels on the corrosion behaviour is discussed.

Keywords: Ion implantation; Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy; Corrosion

1. Introduction

One of the main disadvantages of stainless steels is the problem of localised corrosion when they are exposed to chloride solutions [1]. There are several surface modification techniques to improve stainless steels' behaviour against localised corrosion in such media. One of them is ion implantation [2]. This technique allows the incorporation of almost any element into a very superficial level in a solid. The main difference of ion implantation vs. other surface modification techniques is the formation of a surface alloy of graded composition that possesses no well-defined interface with respect to the substrate without modification of the original dimensions [5-7]. This technique has physical and chemical effects on the surface of the substrate [8]. Changes in composition are accompanied by structural changes because of radiation damage. It is possible to transform the outermost surface layer of the material into another chemical compound and to passive metals by ion bombardment [5-9]. Many surface characteristics are affected in an important way but this treatment does not affect the bulk properties [10].

Stainless steels behaviour against corrosion can be improved by implanting elements like Mo, Cr,

Ti, and Ni which contribute to the formation of the passive layer [9,11,12]. Some of these ions have demonstrated a remarkable corrosion resistance of such layers. However, little information is available on the effect of Si implantation into stainless steels against localised aqueous corrosion. Recently, Baszkiewicz et al. [1,13] and Nishimura et al. [14] have studied the pitting corrosion resistance of silicon implanted stainless steels and concluded that silicon ion implantation inhibits pitting corrosion of these materials.

The aim of this paper is to study the effect of different doses of silicon implantation on two similar stainless steel with different microstructures, such as AISI 304 (austenitic) and AISI 430 (ferritic) in an attempt to improve their corrosion resistance in aqueous solutions containing chloride ions. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersion spectroscopy (EDS) have been used to analyse the localised corrosion behaviour of Si-implanted stainless steels.

2. Experimental method

The stainless steels used in this work are AISI 304 and AISI 430. Their chemical composition are shown in Table 1. For the electrochemical tests, all 4 × 4 cm plate specimens were ground to a surface finish of SiC No. 600 emery paper and implanted with different doses of Si (1×10^{14} , 5×10^{14} , 1×10^{15} ions/cm²) at a fixed energy of 80 keV. Theoretical calculations have been made using the simulation program TRIM96 to provide an idea of the depth profile. Implanted specimens of 1 × 1 cm were characterised by AES in a JEOL JAMP — 50 μA with a 10-μA spot diameter.

The measurements at open circuit potential were started after 20 min of immersion of the samples in a 0.5 M NaCl solution in order to obtain the necessary stability of the system for an AC impedance measurement. The experiments lasted for 5 weeks and were carried out at the open circuit potential with an amplitude of 5 mV in the frequency range from 10 mHz to 30 kHz. All experiments were recorded with a frequency response analyser (Solartron 1255) and a potentiostat (EG & G 283). The impedance spectra were analysed with the simulation Boukamp equivalent circuit software. After the electrochemical tests, samples were cleaned with distilled water, dried and examined by SEM and EDS.

3. Results and discussion

Table 2 shows the projected range (PR) straggle (ΔPR) and the maximum implantation depth obtained for the Si-implanted depth profiles for AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels at 80 keV. They have been calculated by means of TRIM96 computational code. This program is based on Monte Carlo calculations where it was assumed that these steels had a 50-Å thick Cr₂O₃ passivation layer. It can be observed, in both cases, that PR and ΔPR as well as the maximum implantation depth have similar values. This could be explained in terms of the limitations of this program because

it does not take into account the microstructure of the substrate and the implantation doses.

Figs. 1 and 2 represent AES spectra of the outer and inner sublayers of the Si-implanted AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steel, respectively. In both cases, the Augerspectra reveal that Si has diffused outwards showing a maximum contribution on the top of the surface and a small depletion in the sublayers increasing the Si content in the inner region up to that of the as-received steel. The diffusion of silicon is thought to be due to the small size of the element and its ability to become oxidized as can be seen from the left shift of the $Si_{L_{VV}}$ transition (92 eV). In the case of AISI 304 steel, Si is mainly located in a very thin sublayer on the top of the passivation layer, whereas for the AISI 430 steel higher and deeper concentrations of Si are present in the passive film.

Fig. 3 shows the Nyquist and Bode diagrams obtained for all Si-implanted AISI 304 after 1 h exposure time. A reference sample (non-implanted) was also tested for comparison purposes. It can be seen in the Nyquist diagram (Fig. 3a) that the sample implanted with the lowest dose (1×10^{14} ions/cm²) shows a higher corrosion rate than that of the reference as evidenced by the shorter diameter of the semi-circle. However, for doses higher than 5×10^{14} ions/cm², the corrosion rate is lower than that of the reference. The Bode diagram (Fig. 3b) shows a single time constant mechanism for the 1×10^{14} Si-implanted and the non-implanted sample. However, for the most implanted sample (1×10^{15} ions/cm²) the formation of a second peak was observed which corresponds to a second constant time. For intermediate doses, this peak is very small. This change in the impedance electrochemical response can be due to a silicon oxide sublayer on the top of the passive film of 1×10^{15} ions/cm² Si-implanted AISI 304, which improves the corrosion resistance of this steel. This silica-like layer had been already detected by AES (Fig. 1). For the lowest implantation dose (1×10^{14} ions/cm²) radiation damage could be probably more important than the beneficial chemical effects produced by ion implantation.

Fitting of the impedance spectra data for the Si-implanted AISI 304 obtained with the Boukamp simulation program proposes two different models: a Randles circuit for the non-implanted sample and the one implanted with 1×10^{14} ions/cm² and a double layer circuit for the most implanted samples (Fig. 3b). Hong et al. previously suggested the Randles circuit for AISI 304 stainless steel in similar media [15].

Fig. 4 shows Nyquist and Bode diagrams obtained from Si-implanted AISI 304 samples after 72 h exposure time. It can be observed in the Nyquist plot that all the implanted samples presented lower corrosion rates than the non-implanted (Fig. 4a). It is worthy to note the improvement in corrosion behavior of the 1×10^{14} ions/cm² implanted sample in comparison to earlier immersion

times (Fig. 3a). On the other hand, the already mentioned two time constant mechanism of the 1×10^{15} ions/cm² implanted sample tends to disappear in favor of a one time constant mechanism similar to the other samples (Fig. 4b). This phenomenon could be due to the partial chemical dissolution of the outermost passivation silica rich layer with exposure time in the chloride-containing electrolyte. The 1×10^{15} ions/cm² implanted sample tends to disappear in favor of a one time constant mechanism similar to the other samples (Fig. 4b). This phenomenon could be due to the partial chemical dissolution of the outermost passivation silica rich layer with exposure time in the chloride-containing electrolyte.

After 5 weeks of immersion time the Nyquist plot (Fig. 5a) shows that all the implanted samples had slightly lower corrosion rates than the non-implanted one (Fig. 5a). Bode plot (Fig. 5b) shows similar spectra in all cases but some small differences can be observed between the two highest dose implanted samples and the two others. For large periods of immersion, the samples implanted with 1×10^{14} ions/cm² and the non-implanted fit a pitting equivalent circuit proposed by Mansfeld [16]. For higher doses of implantation, EIS spectra fit well with the two-layer model equivalent circuit. SEM examinations revealed the presence of an important density of pits on the non-implanted sample (Fig. 6). On the sample implanted with the lowest dose (1×10^{14} ions/cm²) a large number of pits and bigger than those on the non-implanted sample was also found (Fig. 7). However, the Si-implanted samples with doses above 5×10^{14} ions/cm² exhibited less chemical attack with a lower pit density. Moreover, some dark and isolated products were detected on the surface (Fig. 8a). EDS microanalysis revealed that they are mainly composed of silicon (Fig. 8b).

Fig. 9 shows the Nyquist and Bode diagrams obtained for the Si-implanted AISI 430 after 1 h exposure time. A reference sample (non-implanted) was also tested for comparison purposes. In the case of AISI 430, the EIS spectra showed that the effect of silicon implantation is more important on this steel than on AISI 304. It can be seen in the Nyquist plot (Fig. 9a) that all implanted samples exhibit a slower corrosion rate than the non-implanted one, specially the 1×10^{15} ions/cm² implanted sample whose charge transfer resistance (R_p) is much larger than that of the other samples. In a similar way, the Bode plot (Fig. 9b) showed that all doses of Si-implanted AISI 430 completely modify the one-time constant mechanism of AISI 430 without implantation. The 1×10^{14} and 5×10^{14} ions/cm² implanted samples exhibited a two-time constant mechanism, whereas the most implanted sample indicated a very different behavior with a three-time constant mechanism. It can be also observed that the most noticeable change in the EIS spectra of the Si-implanted AISI 430 took place in the high frequency range. This means that ion implantation changes the outer zones of the passivation layer, which can be attributed to the formation of a silica-like layer, already detected by AES (Fig. 2) more deeper than that formed on AISI 304. However, a second layer

was not detected in our experimental results. This second layer could be an amorphous layer or a Si-Fe phase. Baszkiewicz et al. [13] found a solid amorphous layer on Si-implanted austenitic stainless steels for doses higher than 1×10^{17} ions/cm², the solid amorphous layer responsible for the high corrosion resistance. Feyeulle et al. [17] observed an additional Fe₃Si compound.

The evolution with immersion exposure time of the Si-implanted AISI 430 can be observed in Fig. 10 after 72 h. It can be observed in the Nyquist diagram (Fig. 10a) that all implanted samples presented similar EIS spectra than those at the beginning of the experiment, especially the 1×10^{15} ions/cm² implanted sample. This last one began to show another capacitive loop in the low frequency range that produces higher R_p values and, consequently, a slower corrosion rate. Thus, the Bode diagram (Fig. 10b) for the 1×10^{14} and 5×10^{14} ions/cm² implanted samples exhibits a two-time constant mechanism, whereas the most implanted sample shows the already mentioned three-time constant mechanism. This electrochemical behavior is completely different from that of AISI 304. As already reported, the implanted samples tend to show similar impedance spectra to that of the non-implanted sample after 72 h of immersion.

Fig. 11 shows the Nyquist and Bode diagrams obtained for Si-implanted AISI 430 spectra after 5 weeks of immersion. Corrosion rates of implanted samples decreased with an increase of implantation dose and all of them had slower corrosion rates than the non-implanted one (Fig. 11a). On the other hand, at this time, all the implanted samples maintained analogous corrosion mechanism from the beginning, but with the most superficial layer damaged by a partial chemical dissolution in the electrolyte (Fig. 11b). Note the EIS spectrum of the most implanted sample (1×10^{15} ions/cm²) with a displacement of the reaction peaks to a higher frequency range. A triple layer circuit modified by a partial dissolution of the outer sublayer fits this spectrum, whereas the 1×10^{14} and 5×10^{14} ions/cm² implanted samples are fitted by a double layer circuit (Fig. 11b) also modified by the same phenomenon. AISI 430 without implantation fits the pit circuit proposed by Mansfeld [16]. SEM examinations of the non-implanted sample of AISI 430 revealed a similar appearance to that of AISI 304, but the pits seem to be smaller and deeper (Fig. 12). In the case of Si-implanted samples of AISI 430, the quantity of pits decreased with an increase in the implantation doses after large corrosion times. In this way, some superficial defects of small size were found on the sample implanted with the highest dose (Fig. 13).

In conclusion, the beneficial effects of silicon ion implantation are much more pronounced for the AISI430 than for the AISI 304. Baszkiewicz et al. [13] confirmed the higher corrosion resistance of AISI 430 than AISI 304L with silicon implantation. The improvement of the corrosion behavior of the implanted samples for both stainless steels is due to formation of a silica-like layer on the

outer part of the passive film on both steels (Figs. 1 and 2). However, a new phase could be formed on AISI 430, which produces a three-time constant mechanisms for the highest implantation dose (1×10^{15} ions/cm²). After exposure times longer than 5 weeks, silicon ion implantation delayed the pitting corrosion, their protective effects being more important on AISI 430 than on AISI 304.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Silicon ion implantation is an effective technique to improve the pitting corrosion resistance of both AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels in a 0.5 M NaCl solution. Its beneficial effects are much more pronounced on the AISI 430 and above a critical dose it seems to delay pit nucleation on the AISI 304.
2. Above the critical value of 5×10^{14} ions/cm², silicon ion implantation is effective for the AISI 304 steel against this chloride-containing media. However, a 1×10^{14} ions/cm² dose is enough to provide protection against pitting for the AISI 430 steel.
3. The improvement in resistance to localised corrosion of AISI 304 and AISI 430 steels is due to the formation of a Si-rich sublayer on the outer zone of the passivation layer. This layer modifies the corrosion mechanism of both stainless steels.

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TABLES

Table 1

Chemical composition of AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels

	Si	Mn	Sn	Ni	Cu	Cr	P	Mo	Co	C	S	N
AISI 304	0.44	1.52	0.013	8.19	0.29	18.30	0.031	0.21	0.12	0.065	0.002	0.038
AISI 430	0.32	0.3	-	0.21	0.03	16.53	0.020	0.01	0.02	0.064	0.001	0.032

Table 2

Projected range (PR), staggle (Δ PR) and maximum implantation depth of implanted samples for AISI 304 and AISI 430 stainless steels

	PR (\AA)	ΔPR (\AA)	Maximum depth (\AA)
AISI 304	513	234	=1360
AISI 430	519	236	=1340

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Auger spectra of the 1×10^{15} implanted AISI 304 stainless steel at 80 keV without Ar bombardment (thin line) and with consecutive Ar bombardments (broader lines).

Fig. 2. Auger spectra of the 1×10^{15} implanted AISI 430 stainless steel at 80 kV without Ar bombardment (thin line) and with consecutive Ar bombardments (broader lines).

Fig. 3. Nyquist (a) and Bode (b) diagrams of Si-implanted AISI 304stainless steel with different doses after 1 h of immersion.

Fig. 4. Nyquist (a) and Bode (b) diagrams of Si-implanted AISI 304stainless steel with different doses after 72 h of immersion.

Fig. 5. Nyquist (a) and Bode (b) diagrams of Si-implanted AISI 304stainless steel with different doses after 5 weeks of immersion.

Fig. 6. Superficial appearance of the non-implanted sample of AISI304.

Fig. 7. Detail of some spallation of 1×10^{14} ions/cm² implanted AISI 304.

Fig. 8. General aspect of 1×10^{15} ions/cm² implanted AISI 304 (a). EDS microanalysis of the black products in its surface (b).

Fig. 9. Nyquist (a) and Bode (b) diagrams of Si-implanted AISI 430 stainless steel with different doses after 1 h of immersion.

Fig. 10. Nyquist (a) and Bode (b) diagrams of Si-implanted AISI 430 stainless steel with different doses after 72 h of immersion.

Fig. 11. Nyquist (a) and Bode (b) diagrams of Si-implanted AISI 430 stainless steel with different doses after 5 weeks of immersion.

Fig. 12. Superficial appearance of the non-implanted sample of AISI430.

Fig. 13. General aspect of 1×10^{15} ions/cm² implanted AISI 430.